

First record of *Galeatus scrophicus* Saunders, 1876 (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Tingidae) for Italy

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ABSTRACT: The first record of *Galeatus scrophicus* Saunders, 1876 (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Tingidae) for Italy is reported. Information on the biology and the distribution of the species is summarised.

KEYWORDS: *Galeatus scrophicus*, first record, distribution, Sicily, Italy, Mediterranean Region.

The sunflower lace bug *Galeatus scrophicus* Saunders, 1876 (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Tingidae) is distributed from southern Europe and northern Africa to South Africa, the Middle East and Asia including India (Deckert & Göllner-Scheiding, 2006; Satti & El Khidir, 2013).

The species is oligophagous. Nymphs and adults feed on the leaves of various Asteraceae. In Africa and in the Middle East, *G. scrophicus* is considered a pest on sunflower *Helianthus annuus* L. (Asteraceae) (Satti & El Khidir, 2013; Ellis, 2024).

In Europe, *G. scrophicus* has been reported from Cyprus, Greece (including the island of Crete), Russia (south European part) and Spain, so far (Guilbert et al., 2024; Aukema, 2025).

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The presence of the species in Bulgaria is doubtful (Aukema, 2025).

Herein, the first record of *G. scrophicus* on the island of Sicily which, at the same time, is the first record of the species for Italy, is reported: On 24.08.2024, an adult specimen was found on a beach in the village of Brucoli, located at the eastern coast of the island. A series of related photos (Fig. 1) was uploaded to the online database iNaturalist (Maiorana Montes, 2024).

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Figure 1. Specimen of *Galeatus scrophicus* Saunders, 1876, Brucoli, Sicily, Italy, 24.08.2024. (Photos: Pietro Maiorana Montes).

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